

STRUCTURAL TESTING OF A SLENDER COMPOSITE SLIT-TUBE

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ABSTRACT

Structural behavior of a composite slit tube member is notoriously difficult to predict analytically. Buckling, crippling, and bending stiffness are all difficult to measure on a 5 to 12 meter slender test article. This class of open section member is growing in usefulness for supporting deployable space platforms. A test methodology is developed for measuring the moment-curvature response of these members. The slit tube test article used is 593.6 cm (233.7 in) long, Ø15.2 cm (Ø6 in), and is constructed of a four-ply carbon fiber reinforced polymer laminate. Results showed slit tube bending stiffness to be 25% less when the slit opening was orientated along the maximum distance from the neutral axis as opposed to when it was aligned orthogonal to the neutral axis. A 595.3 cm (234.4 in) long, Ø11.4 cm (Ø4.5 in), simple aluminum tube with fixed boundaries was used to validate the test setup. Measured strains and bending stiffness results matched theoretical closed form values to within 2%. Hysteresis in the moment-curvature data was very low for both test articles. The test approach worked well for measuring moment-curvature and is amenable to measuring axial load-deflection response, column buckling, and combined axial-moment load response.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Storable Tubular Extendible Member (STEM) [1] is a type of deployable boom that resembles a carpenter tape but with a substantially overlapped cross-section. The ease of construction and strain energy deployment simplicity of this structural member has led to the widespread use on spacecraft since the first in 1962, the Canadian satellite Alouette [2], where STEMs were used as the antennas. Historically, STEMs have been constructed from a high strain metallic material such as stainless steel or copper Beryllium. These materials, however, are not dimensionally stable when subjected to the large thermal gradients typical of exposed space flight and are three times lower in specific modulus than carbon fiber composite laminates.

Over the years, several new embodiments of the STEM have been adapted to spacecraft applications. For example, non-overlapped STEMs are used as compression columns on rollable solar arrays due to the smaller flattened width and simpler construction techniques compared to STEM booms [3]. Those with subtend (i.e., cross-section) angles of less than 180° are known as tape hinges, while those with subtend angles greater than 180° but less than 360° are known as slit tubes, and are the primary focus of this study.

A typical slit tube member is fabricated in the deployed state on a mandrel then collapsed and furled into the stowed state for launch as shown in Figure 1. Slit tube composite laminates are constructed with only a few plies of ultra-thin unidirectional tape and biased weaves to withstand extreme bending strains and to give high axial stiffness when un-furled. Because of the unique bending strength of these laminates, they have been categorized into a special class known as High Strain Composites [4]. This combination of bending resilience, deployed stiffness, and dimensional stability enables slit tube structures to be furled compactly for launch then deployed to a high stiffness state once on-orbit using minimal mechanism control.

There are, however, certain behavior aspects to composite slit tubes that are not well understood analytically. These complexities include the following: boundary end conditions, crippling along free edges, low torsion stiffness that causes twisting under column loads, and the inadequacy of analytical shell elements to predict the combined twisting and crippling edge effects. Many of these challenges may be better understood with reliable experimental data to calibrate analytical predictions. As a result, slit tube designers are forced to use high strength margins and conservative assumptions that hamper structural efficiency.

The Air Force Research Laboratory Space Vehicles Directorate (AFRL) in conjunction with LoadPath are developing the fundamental mechanics understanding of high strain composite laminates both experimentally and analytically [5][6]. The intended outcome of these investments is high quality, dimensionally stable, well understood, composite slit-tube elements. Currently the analytical tools are being developed to accurately predict slit tube stiffness and column strength behavior. In order to validate these models, a comprehensive test program has been initiated to obtain load-deflection and the corresponding stiffness from representative open section elastic composite tube elements.

Figure 1: AFRL/LoadPath slit tube; a) completely stowed, b) partially deployed, and c) fully deployed.

2 TEST DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Testing Considerations

Slit tubes are inherently difficult to test—many factors have to be carefully considered. The goal of this test program was to methodically increase the test complexity until an operational loading environment could be duplicated. Initially, the fundamental, component level properties were measured using tightly controlled load states. The following is a discussion highlighting the key difficulties in testing carbon fiber slit tubes and the justification for this step-wise testing approach

First and foremost, slit tube deformations are affected by the orientation of gravity when tested terrestrially. Typically having a slenderness ratio of up to 150:1, slit tubes are precluded from horizontal testing without an elaborate offload suspension system to simulate weightlessness of micro-gravity spaceflight. Many slit tubes, when extended horizontally, will twist then bend significantly and may even collapse under their own weight. Testing vertically eliminates these issues, but having the appropriate facilities and infrastructure to handle very tall slit tubes is its own limitation. Due to the relatively light axial buckling load limits, the weight of the tube must be accounted for during vertical testing by either offloading or post-test data reduction.

Boundary conditions are perhaps the most challenging aspect of slit tube testing. Load-deformation response is highly sensitive to the end constraints. Ideally, the end conditions would mimic the degrees of freedom at the tube mid-span—a prismatic scenario straightforward to predict analytically. However, this condition is not physically possible due to the twisting and cross-section expansion tendencies of a column or bending loaded slit tube. Therefore the end constraints will always induce a local stress field that is dissimilar from that at the mid-span. The goal then is to minimize this dissimilarity.

Another challenge with the end conditions is ensuring uniform and repeatable load transfer to the test article. Bolted end conditions, for example, are notoriously difficult to predict analytically due to friction effects. End conditions can also be prone to causing stress concentrations that initiate local buckling at the slit edge—a localized response that is not representative of operational use as a deployable structure. Another boundary condition to avoid is the allowance of free rotation about the lengthwise axis. The test article will twist then collapse such as observed during a column test on a composite STEM shown deformed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Composite STEM shown a) unloaded and b) fully herniated under axial compression load.

Instrumentation must also be carefully considered when testing slit tubes. Ideally, full-field, three dimensional, non-contact displacement measurements over the entire length of the test article would be used, albeit this is not a practical instrumentation strategy. More traditional methods such as displacement sensors at the end fittings can be used as long as they do not impart a spring force that could adversely affect the test results. Displacement sensors may also be impractical when attempting to measure large displacements typical of some long slit tubes. In these situations, it can be feasible and sufficiently accurate to make manual measurements with a scale fixed to a reference point. Strain gages can also be considered for thicker laminates that are not sensitive to localized stiffening caused by the adhesive, strain gage, or cabling.

2.2 Test Design and Setup

A test methodology was developed to overcome the aforementioned challenges and was implemented on a $\varnothing 15.2$ cm ($\varnothing 6$ in), 593.6 cm (233.7 in) long carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) slit tube, constructed from a 4-ply laminate using IM7 fibers with an 8552 matrix $[0, \pm 45^\circ \text{PW}, \pm 45^\circ \text{PW}, 0]$. This tube is similar to the one shown in Figure 1. The purpose of this test was to obtain moment-curvature response for comparison to analytical predictions although analytical predictions are beyond the scope of this article. The test article was subjected to a bending moment at the base illustrated in Figure 3 by end conditions, load points, and the free body diagram. Note that the applied moment load creates an equal net tension in the tube. The effects on moment-curvature results are discussed in later sections.

Figure 3: Slit tube a) test setup, b) loading diagram, and c) free body diagram.

Two hydraulic actuators, referred to as the axial actuator and the moment actuator in Figure 4, were used to apply loads to the article. Each actuator had a load cell in-line with the actuator shaft to measure load and to provide feedback to the load control system. The tests were conducted in a freestanding reaction structure frame anchored to a 13.3 cm (5.25 in) thick steel base plate providing a rigid mounting interface for the actuators. The blanchard ground base plate ensures parallelism within .083 mm/m (.001 in/ft).

The end fittings were designed to provide the appropriate boundary conditions at the tube ends and to provide test hardware attachment points. The end conditions were designed to restrain the shear deformation in the tube. Due to the open section of this tube, it is particularly susceptible to twisting. Three 20.3 cm (8 in) long bars were bolted to both boom ends anchored back to an end cap. The bars were clocked at 90°, 180°, and 270° from the slit opening. Two of the end condition bars are shown joining the boom to the moment arm in Figure 4.

Figure 4: a) Slit-tube boundary condition is shown joined to the b) moment arm, axial actuator, and moment actuator.

The axial actuator was aligned with the tube wall. The tube could be clocked around the long axis so the load may be applied along the slit as well as 90° off-axis. The actuator was bolted to the base plate and was pinned on the shaft-to-end fittings connection at the tube root, tube bottom. This pinned

connection was designed to allow a single degree of freedom rotation using ball bearings and tight tolerances to minimize any free-play in the connection. The actuator was also equipped with an anti-rotation fixture to prevent unwanted spinning of the shaft. At the opposite end, the tube tip was attached to the reaction structure with an identical pinned connection that was aligned vertically with the actuator shaft and root pinned connection.

The moment actuator loaded the moment arm in tension, shaft retracting. The moment actuator was positioned 61 cm (24 in) from the axial actuator. Spherical rod ends were mounted on either side of the moment actuator load cell to allow for moment arm rotation and to prevent imparting a moment into the load cell. The axial actuator was configured as previously described. Figure 4 shows the details of the combined axial and moment load setup.

The hydraulic actuator loads were applied as a combined axial and moment load. The axial actuator was actively controlled, but was set to maintain zero load to provide the simplest load case. The test article was therefore subjected to a tension load equivalent to the moment actuator load ramp from zero to 311 N (70 lbf). The hydraulic actuators contained an internal linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) that continuously measured the location/displacement of the actuator shaft while the load was measured with the load cells. The rotation at the test article base was calculated from the net displacement of the axial and moment actuators. Moment load was calculated as the product of the moment arm length and the moment actuator load.

2.3 Test Results

Two load cases were applied to the composite slit tube test article. For the first, the slit was oriented 0° toward the positive x-direction as referenced in Figure 3, loading the slit in maximum compression. For the second case, the slit was oriented 90° counter-clockwise from the first case, pointing the slit in the positive y-direction.

The results of both test cases are shown in Figure 5. Close loading and unloading curves indicates that the test article and the test fixture have low hysteresis. The bending stiffness results for the two test cases are expectedly different. The bending stiffness for the 0° slit orientation is approximately 25% lower than when the slit is oriented 90°. The reason is that the 0° orientation is more compliant is that it places the slit at the maximum distance from the neutral axis.

Figure 5: Moment-curvature results of the composite slit tube test.

3 TEST VALIDATION

An additional testing effort was initiated to assess the validity of the test setup used for the carbon fiber slit tube tests. This was accomplished by duplicating the test setup on a known, simplified test article. By doing so, the complexities of thin-walled, open-section, composite slit tube structures were eliminated, and the test methodology and results could be independently evaluated. The ultimate goal of the validation effort was to identify and quantify any parasitic test effects under similar loading conditions.

3.1 Validation test setup

The chosen validation test article was a 6061-T6 aluminum tube with a closed cross section. This tube was selected based on the availability of the desired length, because it had a bending stiffness of the same order of magnitude of the composite slit tube previously tested, and because it could be tested without the risk of buckling. This tube permitted the use of the same test hardware while allowing the application of load up to and beyond that applied to the composite slit tube. The validation article was loaded higher than the slit tube to exacerbate any potentially detrimental parasitic test effects such as pinned joint friction or binding. The validation tube dimensions and theoretical stiffness are shown in Table 1.

	Validation Tube
Material	6061-T6 Aluminum
Nominal Outside Ø (cm in)	11.43 4.5
Wall Thickness (cm in)	.318 .125
Length (cm in)	594 234
Axial Stiffness, EA/L (N/m lbf/in)	12.84 x 10 ⁶ 7.33 x 10 ⁴
Bending Stiffness, EI (N m ² lbf in ²)	1.18 x 10 ⁸ 4.11 x 10 ⁷

Table 1: Validation test article summary.

The validation test setup was different from the slit tube test setup in two aspects. Rather than a bolted connection at the end fittings, the aluminum validation tubes were bonded into a 2.06 cm (.81 in) deep groove machined into a 2.54 cm (1.00 in) thick aluminum end fitting. This machined groove was oversized to provide a nominal .05 cm (.020 in) bond line on the tube inside and outside diameters. Great care was taken to ensure the tube end fitting was bonded perpendicular to the tube’s longitudinal axis each and to maintain clocking between the opposing end fittings. The second change implemented was to move the axial load line of action from the slit tube edge opposite the slit to coincident with the longitudinal axis. Both changes were made to simplify the setup—to remove the potential for slippage in fasteners, and to eliminate bending in the tube due to on off-axis axial load.

Figure 6: Validation tube #1 clamped for alignment during bonding to end fitting.

To help define subsequent instrumentation and load application orientations, the coordinate system, shown in Figure 7, has been established. The X-Y plane is defined as the bottom surface of the root end fitting with the +Z-axis pointing upwards.

Figure 7: Verification testing coordinate system.

Instrumentation was added to help quantify the results of the validation testing. In addition to the LVDT's that monitor the actuator shaft locations, four strain gages and four displacement sensors were used. The uni-axial strain gages were placed on the outside diameter, at the tube mid-span, oriented along the tube axis. They were placed at 90° clocking—0°, 90°, 180°, and 270°. The displacement sensors, all similar to the one shown in Figure 8, consist of sensors mounted to an isolated reference frame, free and clear of any secondary interaction with the test article or hydraulic actuators, allowing only the spring loaded probes to contact the test article end fittings. In this configuration, the sensors measure the tube axial displacement relative to the fixed ground plate. Descriptions of strain gages, displacement sensors, and LVDTs are given in Table 2.

Figure 8: Example displacement sensor setup.

Sensor Type	Instrumentation Channel Name	Aximuth	Distance from Centerline (cm in)	Orientation	Measurement
Strain Gage	STRAIN-1-000	0°	5.72 2.25	Z-Axis	Axial strain
Strain Gage	STRAIN-1-090	90°	5.72 2.25	Z-Axis	Axial strain
Strain Gage	STRAIN-1-180	180°	5.72 2.25	Z-Axis	Axial strain
Strain Gage	STRAIN-1-270	270°	5.72 2.25	Z-Axis	Axial strain
Displacement Sensor	ROOT-1-000	0°	7.62 3.00	Z-Axis	ROOT end fitting rotation
Displacement Sensor	ROOT-1-180	180°	7.62 3.00	Z-Axis	ROOT end fitting rotation
Displacement Sensor	ROOT-1-270	270°	7.62 3.00	Z-Axis	Axial displacement at ROOT end fitting
Displacement Sensor	TIP-1-270	270°	7.62 3.00	Z-Axis	Axial displacement at TIP end fitting
Actuator LVDT	Axial-Disp-1	on-center	0	Z-Axis	Displacement of axial actuator
Actuator LVDT	Moment-Disp-1	180°	68.58 27.00	Z-Axis	Displacement of moment actuator

Table 2: Instrumentation descriptions.

3.2 Validation test results

The validation tube was subjected to the loading state shown in the free body diagram previously shown in Figure 3 except that the moment arm was slightly longer at 68.6 cm (27 in) and the tube was 595.3 cm (234.4 in) long, $\text{Ø}11.4$ cm ($\text{Ø}4.5$ in). Initially, the axial actuator was commanded to apply a compressive load of 240 N (54 lbf) to offload the weight of the test article and end fittings. Once the offload was applied, all instrumentation channels were zeroed and recorded as the baseline, unloaded data set. The moment actuator was then gradually increased until the maximum moment of 610 N m (5,400 in lbf) was applied. During moment application, the axial actuator was continuously commanded to a load level equal and opposite to the moment actuator to eliminate the unwanted, resultant axial load that was present during the slit tube test. The load sequence was reversed to remove the load from the structure. The load profile for the axial and moment actuators along with the net applied moment is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Validation tube load profile.

Using the equation shown in Figure 3c, the validation tube, root bending stiffness (EI) can be calculated from the applied moment and the measured rotation of the root end fitting. These calculations are plotted against the theoretical bending stiffness along with the moment applied to the tube root in Figure 10. As shown, the bending stiffness error starts very high at very small applied loads, but shows much better agreement at $\sim 2\%$ at maximum load.

Figure 10: Validation tube measured and theoretical bending stiffness.

Strains at the validation tube mid-span also show excellent correlation between the measured and theoretical values. As shown in Figure 10, the strains on the applied moment neutral axis remain near zero while the maximum and minimum strain values are consistent with the theoretical values—the largest error was seen at maximum applied moment where the maximum strain differs from the theoretical value of $140 \mu\epsilon$ by $3 \mu\epsilon$, or 2%.

Figure 11: Validation tube mid-span strains.

4 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Many challenges to testing composite slit tubes have been identified and evaluated. A test methodology was developed to address these challenges, and a composite slit tube was tested. Results from the test showed bending stiffness to be 25% less when the slit was orientated in full compression than when it was aligned closer to the neutral axis of the applied moment. Hysteresis in the test article and test setup is very low since unloading curve returned to a near-zero displacement state. The setup appeared to work well, but it became evident that there was a potential for unknown test induced errors that could not be evaluated during a relatively complex composite slit tube test program.

As a result, a simple, aluminum validation tube test was initiated to investigate potential test errors. This validation test used the same test setup as the slit tube. Results showed that measured strains and bending stiffness values matched theoretical to within 2% while the test again exhibited very low hysteresis.

The bending test methodology was demonstrated to be viable for measuring the moment-curvature behavior and the corresponding bending stiffness of long slender tubes and slit tubes. The axial actuator proved to be effective at offloading the test article mass as well as negating the net axial load created by the moment actuator. The axial actuator was successfully used at higher load levels than required for the slit tube test with no apparent friction effects. Validating the test to higher load levels allows future load cases to include column preloading or buckling for more operationally relevant loading scenarios.

Two best practices were developed through the validation test. Additional displacement sensors at the tube root proved more accurate in measuring tube rotation than by calculating rotation from the actuator displacement, ultimately eliminating measurement error caused by bending of the moment arm under load. Secondly, adding strain gauges to the tube walls proved highly valuable as a secondary witness of load-deflection response.

Future testing will include more composite slit tube bending tests as well as direct column loading to determine axial stiffness and buckling. These tests will include a range of diameters, lengths, and subtend angles as well as alternate laminates and material systems. In addition, a boundary condition sensitivity study is planned in order to measure the effects of more flight-like end conditions.

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